

Effect of Digital Manufacturing and Consumer Behaviour on firm Sustainability in Malaysia

Hares Mohammed¹ Danjuma Tali Nimfa¹, Livinus Nkuri Maimako¹
and Ibraheem Rislan Idris²

¹Putra Business School,
Universiti Putra Malaysia,
Malaysia

²Department of Marketing,
Univeristy of Jos,
Nigeria

Email:

Abstract - The organisational perspective on consumer behaviour in the digital manufacturing sector is always seen as a primary concern in the management reality of the company. The purpose of this study was to examine the effect of digital manufacturing and consumer behaviour on firm sustainability in Malaysia. It also investigates the mediating effect of financial structure on the relationship between digital manufacturing and consumer behaviour on firm sustainability. The survey data were received from 102 manufacturing firms in Malaysia and examined using partial least squares structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM) through SmartPLS. The findings of this study have shown that technology has a direct positive relationship with consumer behaviour on firm sustainability in Malaysia. Relatedly, automation has a direct positive relationship with consumer behaviour. However, the findings revealed that there was no direct significant link between the industrial revolution 4.0 and consumer behaviour on firm sustainability. This study also confirmed the direct positive effect of technology on the financial structure. Similarly, the result indicated that automation has a direct relationship with financial structure on firm sustainability, inversely industrial revolution 4.0 did not have a direct relationship with financial structure. In addition, financial structure has a direct positive relationship with consumer behaviour on firm sustainability. The study further reported that financial structure fully mediates between technology and consumer behaviour on firm sustainability. Again, financial structure partially mediated between automation and consumer behaviour on firm sustainability. However, financial structure did not mediate between industrial revolution 4.0 and consumer behaviour on firm sustainability. This current study offer a new theoretical contribution by integrating a novel insight to link the relationship between digital manufacturing components of (technology, automation and industry revolution 4.0), financial structure and consumer behaviour on firm sustainability, also mediating effect of financial structure between technology, automation and industrial revolution 4.0 on consumer behaviour on firm sustainability that has never been studied before in the existing the literature. This study suggests that managers of manufacturing firms should always take consumer behaviour into account when making, strategic planning decisions in the contemporary increase of digital manufacturing business for the firm consumers in Malaysia.

Keywords: Digital manufacturing, technology, automation, industrial revolution 4.0, financial structure, consumer behaviour, firm sustainability.

1. Introduction

The consumer of the late 20th century is a completely new character, one of the strategic variables in terms of consumer behaviour and buying decision (Basile, 2019). The organisational perspective on consumer behaviour in the digital manufacturing sector is always seen as a primary concern in the research and management reality of the company. Managers working in digital manufacturing, with a view to proposing an appropriate system of offerings to clients, would like to understand what motivates consumers to make their day-to-day behaviour towards purchases or which characteristics that influence the process. Improving an eco-friendly image provides an opportunity for companies to attract consumers who influence their buying behaviour on the basis of attitudes and beliefs about their environmentally sustainable technologies, social commitments and firm information (Ameer & Othman 2012; Chen, Tang, Jin, Li, Paillé 2015). In other words, encourages a growing sustainable strategy to characterise their image as sustainable business firms (Nyame-Asiamah & Kawalek, 2020).

Accordingly, consumers are persons who, through their decisions and choices, seek to increase their satisfaction as well as to take on the role of the most powerful driver in the market influence of an enterprise (Migdał-Najman, Najman & Badowska, 2020; Armstrong, 2009). Consumer behaviour is influenced by lifestyle choices, personality traits and economic situations in Malaysia (Pantano, 2011). The internal and external focused sustainable strategies is that a better eco-friendly image presents an opportunity for firms to attract consumers who form their buying behaviours based on their attitudes and beliefs towards firms' environmentally friendly innovations, social commitments and regulatory expectations (Ameer & Othman 2012; Chen, Tang, Jin, Li, Paillé, 2015). In other words lead to an increasing sustainable initiative by companies to register their images as sustainable organizations (Nyame-Asiamah & Kawalek, 2020).

In addition, consumer behaviour is influenced by lifestyle choices, personality traits and economic situations in Malaysia (Pantano, 2011). Smart devices affect consumer behaviour, in terms of the ability to control electronic devices automatically, home automation, internet, hardwired systems and growth in technology (Ordieres-Meré et al., 2020) that was related to digital manufacturing. Other factors affecting consumer behaviour include the integration of electronic interfaces, hardware and information sharing via the internet. Hence, this has resulted in insufficient protection of the promoter, increased inconvenience toward consumer lifestyles, personality, turbulent economic circumstances and financial terms of agreement and the new pandemic influences the consumer behaviour. Mostly with the help of a technology firm, the path of transition from previous methods to digital technology with an amazingly speedy management success will reach consumers of all ages and meet their expectations, connecting whether offline or online (Jose, 2017). "The main drivers of consumer behaviour: information, e-commerce, digitalization, the Internet of Things, e-distribution, technology, digitalization, automation, personalized, performance, artificial intelligence, behaviour intention, e-shopping, and data mining" (Sima, Gheorghhe, Subić & Nancu, 2020). Therefore, in an attempt to address this consumer behaviour challenges integrating digital manufacturing components such as technology, automation and industrial 4.0 on the consumer behaviour trends in the current dynamic environment would be necessary. Adoption of digitalization has become a must for consumers, transforming their current behaviour form traditional decisions to online purchase behaviour (Srinivasan, Rutz

& Pauwels, 2016; Wu & Chang, 2016). As the internet has become easily accessible, consumers are relying on the internet for their daily needs and even customizing their needs with the help of digital technology. Thus, to consumers, it has become a core priority to adopt the technological process to meet their demands. Evidence from past studies has confirmed that maintenance of customer strategic partnership is the core business of any firm (Royle & Laing, 2014).

Despite extensive research on different concepts of digital manufacturing and its components like (technology, automation and IR4.0), financial structure and consumer behaviour. Not all of the components mentioned have been examined intensively. Thus, this study is primarily interested in understanding whether digital manufacturing components such as technology, automation and IR4.0 can improve consumer behaviour for firm sustainability, and also investigating the mediating effect of the financial structure between the three components of digital manufacturing (technology, Automation and IR4.0) on consumer behaviour for sustainability. Because of paucity of study in the area, the authors believe that this would provide a novel insight into the consistent shift in consumer behaviour for firm sustainability.

The focus of this study was to investigate whether the effect of digital manufacturing can enhance consumer behaviour for the sustainability of firm in Malaysia, and the main research question was to what extent has digital manufacturing positively increased consumer behaviour for the sustainability of firm in Malaysia? The main objective of this study was to examine the effect of digital manufacturing on consumer behaviour for the sustainability of the firm, with the focus of this study on consumer behaviour for the sustainability of the firm. The following section covers the empirical reviews and hypotheses development, research methods, results and discussion of the findings, the theoretical contribution, the practical implications, the limitations of the study and concluded.

2. Empirical Reviews and Hypotheses Development

2.1 Consumer behaviour

Consumer behaviour can generally be studied at both the individual and the organisational level, which is the practise of consumers to pursue, make choices, utilise and organise products or services, experience and/or belief in satisfying their needs and their influence on consumers and society (Schiffman & Kanuk, 2007). The rudimentary dependence of the owner-oriented firm was that consumers are central to all business circles (Hogg, Askegaard, Bamossy & Solomon, 2006; Nicholls & Lee, 2006). Marketplace itself means consumers all over the place where all strategic market processes are expressed and applied. In addition to achieving competitive advantage in the marketplace, managers use different value-creating approaches to end-products that reach the hands of consumers. This facilitates consumer behaviour towards increasing the level of patronage and satisfaction of needs (Ezie & Nimfa, 2016). Ashraf (2019) argued that market managers should constantly study the behavioural patterns of their consumers before planning to purchase products or services sold to consumers as the variables explored in this study show that they strongly shape consumer buying patterns. Therefore, integrating digital revolution in manufacturing has moved from single technologies to unified systems. The industrial revolution leads the digital manufacturing to an intelligent, connected, more integrated production that can better the consumers' behaviour through the new changes.

Ansari (2019) pointed out that trust, including trust disposition, institutional based trust, and trust-based intentions, can have a significant influence on consumer behaviour.

2.2 Technology and Consumer Behaviour

The technological advancement, consumer behaviour and e-commerce environment are some of influencing factors for the changing patterns of consumer decision making process (Srinivasan et al., 2016; Wu et al., 2016). Digital technology has changed the thinking and expectations of millennial consumers in terms of acting as the creator of technology connoisseurs who have also shaped the heritage of this link and of future generations (Indahingwati et al., 2019). Technology perceptions show a few predictive capabilities, while cultural beliefs have an insignificant direct effect on the use of technology (Cruz- Cárdenas et al., 2019).

Online retailers are facing challenges for this changing pattern in consumer behaviour. Marketers, manufacturers and retailers are focusing to develop strategies considering the influencing factors. Relatedly, Nimfa, Yunus, Latiff, Mahmood and Wahab (2019) found that there was a significant relationship between all the variables involve such as innovation and customer satisfaction, creativity and competitiveness, technology utilisation and value creation for sustainability of the enterprises. Consumer shopping habits have completely changed over the past decades. Technology has changed the entire scenario in the case of consumer behaviour (Indahingwati et al., 2019). People around the world are now more technology oriented. Nimfa and Goyit (2016) advanced that a positive and significant relationship exists between business incubation technology and business opportunities for sustainable development. As a result, marketers and manufacturers are forced to embrace the technological evolution. Over the last few years the use of mobile devices for shopping activities has grown significantly.

Consumers are now more involved in social media, online opinions, mobile devices payments and many more. One of the biggest influencers in consumer behaviour is social media. All consumers are now engaged with social media and this platform affect the consumer decision making processes. It has been observed consumers look over the online reviews before buying any product. Some consumers consider online reviews as a matter of quality assurance. According to Amblee and Naveen, (2011) when customers take a purchase decision, there are positive or negative information available in electric media, in addition to their own evaluation and experience, when it comes to the source of online reviewer often depend on the experiences and recommendations from others. Technology has provided an upper hand to consumers and with it they decide which products to buy. Based on the discussion above the study hypothesize as:

H₁: There is a significant association between technology and consumer behaviour on firm sustainability.

2.3. Automation and Consumer Behaviour

Automation is referred to as the “automatic control of the manufacture of a product through a number of successive stages; the application of automatic control to any branch of industry or science; by extension, the use of electronic or mechanical devices to replace human labor” (Oxfords English Dictionary, 2006, Frohm, Lindström, Stahre & Winroth, 2008). Automation can be described as a progression of manual through to full automatic operational activities (Parasuraman et al., 2000). On the other side, automation inproduction has brought a significant change in manufacturing industry. With technological evolution where the whole environment in businesses are changing, manufacturing industry

is also getting influenced by it. Basically companies have a big advantage of adopting automation. Automation can be defined as the adoption of automated machines that needs minimal human interaction, robotics logistics and sensors-actuators in production process to have maximum production with minimum level of error (Linner, 2013). As consumer behaviours are changing in this digital era and a big portion of consumers are shifting towards online shopping sites, it becomes essential for manufacturers to adopt automated production process. The automation in production helps to reduce inventory cost for companies, production errors and also labour cost (Linner, 2013).

Additionally, at the manufacturing level, skill diversity and team approaches was considered as complementary to flexible automation interacted positively (Parthasarthy & Sethi, 1993, Adler, 1988). The concept of automation among consumers is perceived differently by scholars. Consumers who are not familiar with technology often resist automation and technology (Reed et al. 2012). For example, people from Generation X are not tech friendly, they resist in automation. But Generation Y, Z and millennials are born in tech era, as a result they are not only familiar but also habituate to automation. Basically the acceptance of automation among consumers can be classified as a generation thing. People often resist new things which is unfamiliar to them. It can be seen in production automation, automation in organization (Erikson 1986; Parasuraman and Riley 1997; Rifkin 1996). Relatedly, workers or employees feel irritated when company brings changes in working or production process. So, before bringing any automation in the process, it must be introduced to people, thus the automation process will be more acceptable. Based on this discussion, the developed hypothesis can be:

H₂: There is a significant association between automation and consumer behaviour on firm sustainability.

2.4 Industrial Revolution (IR 4.0) and Consumer Behaviour

There has been a huge development in communication and information technology after third industrial revolution. In this fourth phase of industrial revolution, the whole world is covered by big data, internet and of course information technology. The E-commerce sector has shown tremendous growth which outpaced the growth of the traditional retail business sector. The worldwide sales of the retail E-commerce sector recorded 2.3 trillion US dollars in 2017, and is expected to rise around 4.88 trillion dollars by 2021 (Statista 2018). Consumers are shifting more towards online consumption rather than going for the malls. A big change can be observed in consumers' buying behaviour. According to N. R. Narayana Murthy, co-Founder, Infosys, "It is a well-known fact that bringing in technologies in the production sector is good for customers."

In IR 4.0 the actual factor which is influencing all the sectors is internet. With the availability of internet most of the customers are now coming internet and it has become a big platform for marketers, retailers to attract consumers. According to P. Usha Vaidehi (2014), males are more interested to buy online compare to female consumers as it saves time and energy. In India, it has been observed that most online consumers are students (Khare & Rakesh, 2011). Comegys and Brennan (2003) conducted a study in US and Ireland and in that study they found that young people spend on an average 7 to 12 hours on the internet and most of them uses smartphones to access the internet. Moeuf, Pellerin, Lamouri, Tamayo-Giraldo & Barbaray (2018) states that the concepts of industry 4.0 had slightly been adopted by SMEs in the industrial operations mainly for monitoring purposes but however, the actual

applications in production planning perspective was lacking. Therefore, some scholars perceive the impact of IR 4.0 positively and some perceive negatively. According to Comegys and Brennan (2003), over use of internet exploit the mental health of humans. On the other side Hermann, Pentek and Otto (2016) explains the advantages of IR 4.0 in human life. Hence, some contradictions can be seen in the relationship between IR 4.0 and consumer behaviour. Thus, the following has been advanced:

H₃: There is a significant association between industrial revolution 4.0 and consumer behaviour on firm sustainability.

2.5 Financial Structure as a Mediating Variable

Lin, Sun & Jiang (2009) define “financial structure” as the composition and relative importance of various financial institutional arrangements in a financial system. Beckett (1998) noted that management problems affecting businesses with knowledge of consumer behaviour recognised that the financial structure of the strategic and operational challenges of businesses depends on the type of consumer behaviour or potential customers. The financial structure is significantly linked to financial access of consumers, enhanced consumer financial planning behaviour is related to improved financial access (Erkol & Coşkun, 2020; Birkenmaier & Fu, 2019; Aghion, Bond, Klemm & Marinescu, 2004).

Likewise, Consistent organisational core values are reflected in the future behaviour of the management team, which will have a high impact on the public dimension and a higher consumer behaviour component (Perez & del Bosque, 2009). Morally acceptable consumer behaviour would lead to improved understanding of the financial structure of consumer-business sustainability and greater satisfaction (Perez & del Bosque, 2009; Oro and Ekpo, 2020). At the end of the day, ethical behaviour of consumers would enhance the company's response, such as increased consumer response time or promotional ideas about the reality of the situation (Murray & Vogel, 1997).

Evidence from prior studies have found that ‘the financial structure of firms belonging to the same industry classification generally have similar financial structures whereas firms from different industry classes generally displayed different financial structures’ (Schwartz & Aronson, 1967; Lin, Sun & Jiang, 2009; Wang & Li, 2020; Chu, 2020; Saraswati, Maski, Kaluge & Sakti, 2020; Salomon & Klaus-Jürgen, 2017). According to Hsieh, Chen and Lin (2019) income inequality increases with financial deepening but decreases with a more market-oriented financial system for sustainability of the enterprises which is related to consumer behaviour and perceptions. Vanhanen (2020) suggested that robotic process automation (RPA) can be used to effectively automate various business operations that are high in volume, manual, repetitive, based on a certain set of clear rules and are in a stable information technology (IT) environment.

The potential for workplace automation gives firms the option to reduce labour-induced operating leverage, allowing them to adopt less conservative financial policies (Bates, Du & Wang, 2020; Chiu, Wang & Vasarhelyi, 2020). Relatedly, sophisticated precedence relationships exist among various sustainability functions of Industry 4.0 (Ghobakhloo, 2020; Pickard, Grecu & Grecu, 2019; Tuffnell, Kral, Durana & Krulicky, 2019; Hayhoe, Podhorska, Siekelova & Stehel, 2019). Relatedly, García-Muiña, Medina-Salgado, Ferrari and Cucchi, (2020) results illustrated the new company’s sustainable value proposition, considered all the three pillars of sustainability such as environment, economy, and society. Results from Dahlin et al. (2020) indicated that a substantial commitment to CSR is

positively linked to a longer-term financial structure. According to Kramer and Porter (2011), firms are reshaping their business processes in terms of both financial structure, firm performance and sustainability actions, in order to focus on the core belief of consumers.

The consumer is more inclined to interact in digital manufacturing activities with a greater tendency to obtain view of the firms' financial structure. Therefore inclusion of financial structure as a mediating variable would bring novel insight into relating the indirect effect of digital manufacturing component such as (technology, automation and IR 4.0) on consumer behaviour for the firm sustainability which was lacking in the extant literature (Ahmed et al., 2019). Based on the assertions above, the financial structure as a mediating variable revealed insufficient empirical research. Therefore, this current research seeks to bridge the knowledge gaps by introducing the financial structure to mediate the effect of digital manufacturing through its three components such as (technology, automation and IR 4.0) and consumer behaviour on firm sustainability, especially in Malaysia. Thus, the following hypotheses were suggested as:

H4a. Financial structure mediates the effect of technology and consumer behaviour on firm sustainability.

H4b. Financial structure mediates the effect of automation on consumer behaviour for sustainability of firm.

H4c. Financial structure mediates the effect of IR 4.0 and consumer behaviour on firm sustainability.

2.6 Diffusion of Innovation (DOI) Theory

The theory (DOI) had been propounded in 1962 by E. M. Rogers, it is one of the earliest theory in strategic management and social science. It was instigated through an interaction to describe how an idea/product is gaining strength over time and diffusing or spreading via a particular population or social system (LaMotte, 2019). The final outcome in this diffusion would be that people, embrace a new idea, behaviour, or product as part of a social system. Adopting implies that a person would do something different from what they had before for instance purchasing or using a new product, adopting and practicing a new behaviour. The best approach for adopting is that the individual must see the idea, behaviour patterns or product as new or innovative. As a result of this diffusion can be accomplished. Digital technology-based autonomous consumers usually control the option of manufacturers (Gasnov, Zubarev, Krasota, (2020). Often throughout the diffusion process a digital software is transmitted via a social system mechanism across the contact medium linked to the consumers of the manufacturing firm.. This in turn promote the effectiveness of manufacturing firms in meeting their sustainability goals with the rapidly growing digital market economy by satisfying the consumer needs. According to previous work of scholars, there are five major factors influencing the adoption of innovation, they include relative advantage, compatibility, complexity, triability and observability (Rogger 1983, 1995; Angelmar, 1990). The use of digital manufacturing technologies (DMTs) is changing the face of the manufacturing landscape and enhancing the competitiveness of firms (Gillani, Chatha, Jajja & Farooq, 2020; Bokrantz, Skoogh, Berlin & Stahre, 2017).

The adoption of a new concept, behaviour or product that is "innovation" never occur simultaneously in the social system; rather, a process in which certain persons are more

capable to adopting innovation than others. Studies have shown that consumers who adopt an innovation at an early stage have different features than those who adopt innovation later on. When promoting an innovation to a target population, it is important to understand the characteristics of the target population that will help or hinder adoption of the innovation. Therefore, any manufacturing firm implementing digital system to serve a target consumers, it is necessary to understand the attributes of the consumers in the market that will influence the adoption of the technological innovation. Based on the focus and context of this research diffusion of innovation theory fits in to explain the convergence of digital manufacturing and its components (technology, automation and IR 4.0), financial structure and consumer behaviour within a single framework to describe the relationship between the selected variables in the study.

2.6 Research Framework

Figure 1 shows the conceptual framework of this study that was derived from the theoretical foundations. This explain the direct relationship between digital manufacturing three components such as technology, automation and IR4.0, financial structure and consumer behaviour on firm sustainability. The framework also connect the indirect effect of financial structure as it mediates the between technology, automation and IR4.0 on consumer behaviour.

Figure 1 Research Framework of Digital Manufacturing and Consumer Behaviour on firm sustainability.

3. Research Methods

The data for this study were collected through the online survey method. The study was undertaken from March -June, 2020. To improve generalising the finding outcomes, the firms for the study were selected using simple random sample via the firms' repository database in Malaysia, where the firms' profiles with the detail information about the

Malaysian manufacturing enterprises. Among random selected firms', each enterprises website was verified to know whether this firms were associated to digital manufacturing and consumer behaviour for sustainability with the products or services delivered. Out of 866 firms contacted only 203 participated in the survey with the response rate of 23.44%. Out of the survey copies of questionnaire retrieved online survey only 102 was used as the final sample size because 76.56% questionnaires were not returned.

Thus, only 102 manufacturing firms were active and had met the required products/services offered. Based on that it allowed for investigating homogenous set of manufacturing firms that have the criteria regarding the digital manufacturing and consumer behaviour on sustainability of firms (Holmström, Liotta & Chaudhuri, 2017; Niaki, Torabi & Nonino, 2019; Ghobakhloo, 2020). In addition, consumer behaviour is a core strategic focus for digital manufacturing firms. Based on the data obtained 48 manufacturing firms were categorised into small enterprises with 5 - 75 employees, while 54 medium enterprises have 75 - 200 employees in accordance with the SMEs definition in Malaysian (SMEsCorp Malaysia, 2015; Razak, Abdullah & Ersoy, 2018). The participants had on a regular basis not less than 10 years practical experience serving in present post. The survey includes 70 business owners and 32 company chief executives (CCEs) of the enterprises who are the decision makers. Therefore, regarding non-response bias, no reminder was being used, p was < 0.05 because less problem of earlier and later respondents considered in this paper.

3.1 Measures

All constructs were measured through a 5-point Likert scale, ranging from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). The reflective scales were used for all constructs (Diamantopoulos & Winklhofer, 2001). To study the novelty this paper used the digital manufacturing components (such as technology measurement were adopted from (Gatignon & Xuereb, 1997; Halac, 2015; Nimfa, Latiff & Wahab 2020), automation measurement were adopted from (Ong, Yee, Hui, Kasim & Hizza, 2015) and measurement for industry 4.0 were adopted from (Imran, Hameed & Haque, 2018), financial structure measurement were adopted from (Ugurlu, 1997; Chittenden et al., 1996) and consumer behaviour measurement were adopted from (Sudbury-Riley & Kohlbacher, 2016) Ethically Minded Consumer Behaviour (EMCB Scale). Furthermore, this paper operationalizes independent variable digital manufacturing through its 3 components (technology, automation and IR 4.0); the dependent variable (consumer behaviour) and the mediating variable (financial structure) through 5 items each. Moreover, this study used variables as unidimensional with a few changes to the research instrument to fit the context of this current study. The items used for the questionnaire design are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Items used for questionnaire Design.

Construct	Code No.	Item	Authors
Technology	TECHN1	Our enterprise is very proactive in the development of new technologies.	Gatignon& Xuereb, 1997;
	TECHN2	Our firm has the capacity to build technological breakthrough	Halac, 2015;
	TECHN3	Our firm has built a strong network of collaboration with suppliers of technological equipment to serve our consumers better.	Nimfa, Latiff & Wahab 2020
	TECHN4	Our firm has an aggressive technological patent strategy	
	TECHN5	Our firm is always the first one to use new technology for its new product to consumers	

Automation	AUTM1	Our automation provides different range of services.	Ong, Yee, Hui, Kasim & Hizza (2015)
	AUTM2	Our automation processes is accurate	
	AUTM3	Our automation delivery is consistent	
	AUTM4	Our automation conducts is dependable.	
	AUTM5	Our automated service is accessible.	
Industrial Revolution 4.0	IR1	It enables the firm to avoid operational downtime and other productivity challenges.	Imran, Hameed, Haque, 2018
	IR2	It relates with responsive, proactive, and predictive practices which enhance the accuracy.	
	IR3	It provides the ability to work in real time.	
	IR4	It offers ways that can successfully address the issues.	
	IR5	It provides the ability to adjust and learn from data.	
Financial Structure	FS1	Our firm financial policy is sensitive to prevailing market.	Ugurlu, 1997; Chittenden et al., 1996; Ferri & Jones, 1979.
	FS2	Our firm possessed propensity for internal/external growth and meet market demand	
	FS3	Our firm has the liquidity to provide market demand	
	FS4	Our firm is sensitive to long-term debt ratio.	
	FS5	Our firm is sensitive to short-term debt ratio.	
Consumer Behaviour	CB1	We often use shopping sites to serve our consumers.	Ansri, 2019 Sudbury-Riley & Kohlbacher, 2016
	CB2	We rely on shopping sites to offer our consumers the best products	
	CB3	We believe internet has made the shopping easier to our consumers	
	CB4	We believe shopping sites provide more facilities to our consumers.	
	CB5	We trust our shopping sites in terms of price and quality to the consumers.	

4. Discussion and Conclusion

4.1 Common Method Bias (CMB)

Common method Bias (CMB) in data analysis is a threat of biased to outcomes of analysis. Common method bias in partial least squares structural equation modelling (PLS-SEM) is spotted through a complete collinearity assessment approach (Kock, 2015). The VIF values must be below the target level of 3.3 (Hair et al., 2019; Hair et al., 2017; Kock, 2015). This would reflect the freedom of the model from the common method Bias (. Higher value over 3.3 indicates that the common method bias has harmed the model. This study evaluates CMB by fulfilling the variance inflation factor (VIF) criteria (Kock 2017; Hair el al., 2019) see Table 5 VIF values of the indicators. Hence, bias from common method Bias was deemed non-existent in this study and was not a major concern.

4.2 Measurement Model Assessment

To investigate the study model, the partial least square structural equation model (PLS-SEM) approach that uses SmartPLS 3.2.9 software was chosen (Hair et al., 2020). This approach was used because, with a vast number of constructs and a non-normal data distribution, partial least squares (PLS) can manage multiple structural equation models (Akter, Wamba & Dewan, 2017; Nor-Aishah et al., 2020). To perform PLS-SEM analysis, the measurement

model was first assessed to ensure the validity and reliability of the study model. This included analyses of composite reliability, convergent validity, and discriminant validity. The measurement model is illustrated in figure 2. Reliability was measured using Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability (CR), which should be above 0.7 and 0.8, respectively (Hair et al., 2014). Meanwhile, convergent validity was measured based on average variance extracted (AVE) values, which should be above 0.5 (Hair et al., 2014, Hair et al., 2019). As shown in Table 2, all the constructs in the study met these criteria and thus displayed satisfactory reliability and convergent validity. Next, discriminant validity for the model was assessed using the heterotrait-monotrait (HTMT) ratio of correlations, which should be less than 0.85 (Voorshees et al. 2016). Based on Table 3, the study constructs met the discriminant validity criteria as well. Finally, the study model was tested for multicollinearity based on the items' variance inflation factor (VIF). Table 4 indicates that all items had VIF values which met the criteria between $3 \geq 5$ (Hair et al. 2017, Hair et al., 2019), which proved the non-existence of multicollinearity issues in this study. As the study model exhibited sufficient reliability and validity, the structural model was subsequently analysed to test the hypotheses.

Table 2 Convergent Validity, Cronbach's Alpha, Composite Reliability (CR) AVE

Construct	Items	Loadings	Cronbach's Alpha	CR	Ave
Technology	TECHN1	0.747	0.743	0.829	0.596
	TECHN2	0.797			
	TECHN 3	0.749			
	TECHN 4	0.532			
	TECHN 5	0.667			
Automation	AUTMN1	0.761	0.754	0.836	0.510
	AUTMN2	0.705			
	AUTMN3	0.829			
	AUTMN4	0.698			
	AUTMN5	0.543			
Industrial revolution 4.0	IR1	0.919	0.838	0.847	0.674
	IR2	0.881			
	IR3	0.791			
	IR4	0.730			
	IR5	0.870			
Financial Structure	FS1	0.864	0.910	0.933	0.735
	FS2	0.891			
	FS3	0.827			
	FS4	0.850			
	FS5	0.853			
Consumer Behaviour	CB1	0.806	0.876	0.910	0.669
	CB2	0.841			
	CB3	0.746			
	CB4	0.859			
	CB5	0.834			

Table 3 Heterotrait- Montriat Ratio

	Automation	Consumer Behaviour	Financial structure	Industrial Revolution 4.0	Technology
Automation					
Consumer Behaviour	0.040	0.445			
Financial structure	0.475	0.409			
Industrial Revolution 4.0	0.498	0.461	0.389		
Technology	0.051	0.561	0.459	0.477	

Table 4 Inner VIF

	Consumer Behaviour	Financial Structure
Automation	3.732	3.298
Consumer Behaviour		
Financial Structure	2.445	
Industrial Revolution 4.0	1.166	1.156
Technology	3.612	3.307

4.3 Structural Model Assessment

Table 5 shows the results for the path coefficient analysis for the direct hypotheses (H1 to H7). Overall, all the direct hypotheses were supported.

5. Direct Effect

Table 5.1 There is a significant relationship between technology and consumer behaviour for firm sustainability.

Hypotheses	Relationship	Std. Beta	SE	T Value	P Values	Decision
H1	Technology -> consumer behaviour	0.569	0.116	2.933	0.004	Supported

Table 6.1 revealed that technology has a direct positive relationship with consumer behaviour ($\beta = 0.559$, $t = 2.933$, $p < 0.05$). Therefore, H1 was supported. The connection between technology and consumer behaviour was supported by diffusion of innovation theory. The theory view that technology relates positively with consumer behaviour for firmsustainability in Malaysia. This finding was consistent with the related study in other settings (Fain & Roberts, 1997; Sue, 2015; Jose, 2017; Basile, 2019).

Table 5.2 There is a significant relationship between automation and consumer behaviour for firm sustainability.

Hypotheses	Relationship	Std. Beta	SE	T Value	P Values	Decision
H2	Automation -> consumer behaviour	6.051	0.127	6.904	0.000	supported

Table 5.2 indicated that automation has a direct positive relationship with consumer behaviour $\beta = 6.051$, $t = 6.904$, $p < 0.05$, therefore, hypothesis four (2) was supported. Theory suggested that automation relates positively and was significant with consumer behaviour in Malaysia Nigeria. The connection between automation and consumer behaviour was also supported by the diffusion of innovation theory described in the theoretical framework. The effort to acknowledge the effect of automation has regularly received keen attention by prior researches (Ong et al., 2015; Martiskova & Svec, 2019). Likewise, Paddeu & Parkhurst (2020) supported that changing consumer behaviour is urging firms to produce small quantities in a relatively large number of varieties in a flexible manner and to save a lot of time. The need to better serve consumers can be influenced by automated processes, and this would only be achieved if an increased level of automation is implemented in manufacturing processes.

Table 5.3 There is a significant relationship between industrial revolution 4.0 and consumer behaviour on firm sustainability.

Hypothesis	Relationship	Std. Beta	SE	T Value	P Values	Decision
H3	Industrial revolution 4.0 -> consumer behaviour	0.431	0.058	0.687	0.492	Not supported

Table 5.3 indicated that industrial revolution 4.0 did not have a direct positive relationship with consumer behaviour $\beta = 0.431$, $t = 0.687$, $p > 0.05$, therefore, hypothesis three was not supported. These results support the view (Tupa, Steiner & Simota, 2017) who stated that industry revolution 4.0 is a relatively new approach, manufacturing processes as a result of new initiatives, reconfigured structures, more sophisticated information technology facilities and associated new risks. Consequently, industrial revolution 4.0 did not have a significant effect with consumer behaviour on firm sustainability.

Table 5.4 There is a significant relationship between technology and financial structure on firm sustainability.

Hypothesis	Relationship	Std. Beta	SE	T-Value	P Values	Decision
H4	Technology -> financial structure	2.772	0.118	3.214	0.001	Supported

Table 5.4 indicated that technology has a direct positive relationship with financial structure $\beta = 2772$, $t = 3.214$, $p < 0.05$, therefore, hypothesis four was supported. The relationship between technology and financial structure was also supported by the diffusion of innovation theory. Theory suggested that technology has a direct significant relationship with financial structure on firm sustainability in Malaysia. This findings was consistent with a related research by (Chakraborty & Ray, 2007; Hoffmann, Laeven & Ratnovski, 2020 and Da Silva, Kovalski & Pagani, 2018) who stated that the level of financial expansion is determined by the initial inequality, the size of the investment and the market structure, whereas the financial structure is influenced by investment technologies, legal and financial enterprises.

Table 5.5 There is a significant relationship between automation and financial structure on firm sustainability.

Hypothesis	Relationship	Std. Beta	SE	T-Value	P Values	Decision
H5	Automation -> financial structure	3.603	0.126	3.060	0.002	Supported

Table 5.5 indicated that technology has a direct positive relationship with financial structure $\beta = 3.603$, $t = 3.060$, $p < 0.05$, therefore, hypothesis five was supported. The relationship

between automation and financial structure was also supported by the diffusion of innovation theory. Theory suggested that automation has a direct significant relationship with financial structure on firm sustainability in Malaysia. These findings support the view of (Lawless, O’Connell & O’Toole, 2015; Bates, Du & Wang, 2020).

Table 5.6 There is a significant relationship between industrial revolution 4.0 and financial structure on firm sustainability.

Hypothesis	Relationship	Std. Beta	SE	T Value	P Values	Decision
H6	Industrial revolution structure -> financial structure	0.973	0.067	0.852	0.395	Not Supported

Table 5.6 indicated that industrial revolution did not have a direct positive relationship with financial structure $\beta = 0.973$, $t = 0.852$, $p > 0.05$, therefore, hypothesis six was not supported. The relationship between industrial revolution and financial structure was also supported by the diffusion of innovation theory. Theory suggested that industrial revolution was not significant with financial structure in Malaysia. These findings was backed by the views of (Corò & Volpe (2020) and Horák (2016) confirming that because of firm failure to acquire new technologies or SMART technologies which required substantial initial investment, and also depend on a robust financial structure and management. Firms cannot interact properly with their consumers, suppliers and customers without capable financial decisions. This, in turn, affects the strong link between the industrial revolution and the financial structure. Cirillo et al. (2020) supported the vital element of the ongoing transition to so-called smart manufacturing in the Industrial Revolution 4.0 and the new generation of emerging technologies.

Table 5.7 There is a significant relationship between financial structure and consumer behaviour on firm sustainability.

Hypothesis	Relationship	Std. Beta	SE	T- Value	P Values	Decision
H7	Financial structure -> consumer behaviour	3.462	0.083	4.201	0.000	Supported

Table 5.7 revealed that financial structure has a direct positive relationship with consumer behaviour and significant with $\beta = 3.462$, $t = 4.201$, $p < 0.05$, hence, hypothesis 7 was supported. Financial structure and consumer behaviour has widely been discussed in past studies by (Davis, 1996; Echeboba & Ananwude, 2016; do Paco et al., 2019). Birkenmaier & Fu, (2019). The findings of this study was consistent with the views of (Lee, Ahn & Shin, 2004; Lee, Kim & Ahn, 2019; Heyman, Deloof & Ooghe (2008) who believed that the financial structure of high-growth companies and those with less tangible assets had a lower percentage of liability, which in turn influenced consumer buying decisions. The firm financial structure involves an interaction between the ability of external financial firms to provide financial resources and consumers with investor expectations for other forms of investment that help in shaping their behaviour (Huyghebaert & Van de Gucht, 2007). The financial structure relates to the level of debt used by a business to finance its activities, this structure directly affects the uncertainty and valuation of the technology firm. The financial managers of the company are committed to establishing the best combination of debt and equity to optimise the financial structure. For both private and public firms, the economic indicators for the analysis of the financial structure are essentially the same. This study was consistent with the vies of (Hamilton et al., 2019; Anuja, 1999).

The study model displayed satisfactory coefficients of determination (R^2), where 79.8 percent of consumer behaviour and 59.1 percent of financial structure was explained by their respective predictors (Table 6). Next, in terms of effect size, Table 7 shows that technology had a small effect on both consumer behaviour and financial structure. Meanwhile, automation and financial structure both had larger effect on consumer behaviour. Finally, industrial revolution 4.0 has no effect on both consumer behaviour and financial structure.

However, Chin et al. (2003) explained that a small effect size does not always reflect the insignificance of the construct, especially when the beta coefficient result is substantial. Thus, all the predictor variables in this study had meaningful effects on consumer behaviour and financial. The final step in the structural model assessment was the test for predictive relevance (Q^2), the results of which are shown in Table 8. According to Hair et al. (2017) and Hair et al., (2019), a value of 0.02 shows small relevance, 0.15 shows medium relevance and 0.35 shows large relevance for endogenous constructs. Based on this criteria, this study's endogenous variables, Automation, financial structure and consumer behaviour, exhibited large predictive relevance values in the model. Figure 3 illustrates the structural model of the study.

Table 6 R square

	R Square	R square Adjusted
Consumer behaviour	0.798	0.790
Financial Structure	0.591	0.590

Table 7 F Square

	Consumer Behaviour	Financial Structure	Effect Size on Consumer Behaviour	Effect Size on Financial Structure
Technology	0.040	0.092	Small	Small
Automation	0.317	0.132	Large	Medium
Industrial revolution 4.0	0.005	0.009	-	-
Financial structure	0.176		medium	-

Table 8 Predictive Relevance (Q^2)

	SSO	SSE	Q^2 (=1-SSE/SSO)
Technology	510.000	510.000	
Automation	510.000	510.000	
Industrial Revolution 4.0	510.000	510.000	
Financial Structure	510.000	295.506	0.421
Consumer Behaviour	510.000	246.255	0.517

4.4 Mediation Effect Assessment

In evaluating the effect of mediator using partial least square structural equation model (PLS-SEM). This study used the approach of (Ramayah et al., 2018 and Hair et al., 2017; Sarstedt et al.; 2020). The mediating effect of financial structure on the relationship between digital manufacturing (technology, automation, and industrial revolution 4.0) and consumer behaviour was analysed using the Hair et al (2019) bootstrapping method 5000 re-sampling. The analysis results, shows in Table 10, indicated that financials structure significantly mediates the influence of technology automation model on consumer behaviour. While, financial structure did not mediate between industrial revolution 4.0 and consumer behaviour. In addition, the mediation effect was evident because technology through

financial structure has an indirect effect on consumer. Also, automation through financial structure has an indirect effect on consumer behaviour. However, industrial revolution 4.0 through financial structure did not have any indirect effect on consumer behaviour. The analysis was confirmed the value of confidence interval bias corrected the lower interval (2.50 percent) and upper intervals (97.50 percent) (Hair et al., 2019). Therefore, hypotheses 8 and 9 were supported, while hypothesis 10 was not supported.

Table 9 Indirect Effect Mediation

Hypotheses	Relationship	Std. Beta	SE	T Value	P Value	BCI 2.50%	BCI 97.50%	Decision
8.	Technology -> financial structure -> consumer behaviour	0.110	0.043	2.050	0.041	0.028	0.198	Supported
9.	Automation -> financial structure -> consumer behaviour	0.019	0.045	2.446	0.015	0.046	0.235	Supported
10.	Industrial revolution 4.0 -> financial structure-> consumer behaviour	0.088	0.019	0.995	0.338	-0.023	0.053	Not Supported

4.5. Discussion

This study has provided valuable insights on consumer behaviour in Malaysia. It contributes to the body of knowledge by investigating the direct effect of three components of digital manufacturing (technology, automation and industrial revolution 4.0) on consumer behaviour, as well as the indirect mediating effect of financial structure on digital manufacturing on consumer behaviour that has never been studied in the extant literature. These findings have both theoretical and practical implications. First, the results demonstrate the importance of digital manufacturing in the context of technology, automation and industrial revolution 4.0 on consumer behaviour for sustainability of firm in Malaysia. Specifically, it implies that all construct have direct and indirect effect on consumer behaviour. It also contributes to the strategic management and consumer behaviour literature by examining the unresolved issue concerning the context in another perspective. This study further confirms and strengthens the theoretical view that digital manufacturing and consumer behaviour are important for an enterprises to achieve efficiency in manufacturing sector.

The theoretical framework of this study was also supported by the diffusion innovation theory of the firm, positing the technology advantage as essential tool for manufacturing firm sustainability and addressing issues of consumer behaviour in a global competitive market. This research findings was consistent with the prior study by Gillani, Chatha, Jajja & Farooq (2020) found that the integration of digital technology had a significant effect on the firm performance related to flexibility, design, delivery and quality. Evidence from previous studies further supported that sophisticated design and emerging technology provide new possibilities for manufacturing that is more sensitive, versatile and potentially distributed and situated closer to the consumers (Srai, 2019; Zaki, Theodoulidis, Shapira, Neely & Surekli, 2017). The study also few implications for manufacturers, consumers and financial expert in the manufacturing sectors toward decision making for sustainability of the firm. Managers of manufacturing companies are encouraged to introduce digital manufacturing and create awareness to strengthen consumer behaviour for sustainability and competitive

advantage. In addition, they would strengthen financial structure within their firms to enhance financial flexibility approaches that promote sustainability of the firm.

4.6 Theoretical contribution

In the digital world, related to digital manufacturing, consumers focus on monitoring, once the technology is accepted whether the integration still makes sense to the consumers' behaviour. In other words, the consumer's traits would provide an assessment of the likelihood of the adoption in a specific circumstance and social networks influence the adoption decision of the consumers. The main theoretical contribution of this study is vested in its evaluation upon the correlation of digital manufacturing components such as (technology, automation and industrial revolution 4.0) on consumer behaviour and mediated upon financial structure.

The current issue of consumer behaviour for sustainability of firm has stimulated managers from firms all over the world to react immediately, especially those in the manufacturing firms that are the greatest contributors in the Malaysian economy. While digital manufacturing consists of driving and leading the clusters of consumer behaviour for sustainability of firm towards achieving organizational targets, the relationship between digital manufacturing and consumer behaviour for sustainability of firm is yet to be sustainable performance is yet to be investigated. The current study has drawn novel and insightful conclusions associated with the findings.

The findings verified that technology and consumer behaviour has a significant relationship. This finding was supported by the view of (Wright, 2020), who contributed that the technology, is shifting consumer behaviour and various business activities, making it essential for most firms to transform their business into a new collaborative system due to inter-business functions tailored to their decision-makers. The findings also revealed that automation has a direct positive and significant relationship with consumer behaviour. This result agrees with the findings of previous study investigated by (Martiskova & Svec, 2019). Nevertheless, the findings show that industrial revolution 4.0 did not have a direct significant relationship with consumer behaviour. This finding is consistent with the view of (Tupa et al., 2017). The study, also confirmed that technology has a direct connection with financial structure. In like manner, the result indicated that automation has a direct positive relationship with financial structure. Inversely the study reported that industrial revolution 4.0 did not have a direct positive relationship with financial structure. Moreover, findings revealed that financial structure has a direct positive relationship with consumer behaviour. The study further reported that financial structure fully mediates between technology and consumer behaviour. Again, financial structure partially mediates between automation and consumer behaviour. However, financial structure did not mediate between industrial revolution 4.0 and consumer behaviour. Additionally, this research provides several theoretical contributions with respect to the Diffusion of Innovation Theory (DOI). This result supported DOI, which posits that the digital structure of the new technology decision outlines the key steps that shape consumer behaviour when rethinking the adoption of digital technologies after gaining awareness as well. The consumer behaviour after that form, a perception on the progress could enable the consumer to decide whether to embrace it or not, the use of digital manufacturing thus, allows consumers to continue using the latest technological innovation of their unpredictable nature for sustainability in the firm (Castelo-Branco et al., 2019). Increased digital technology, automation and interconnectivity (Brynjolfsson & McAfee 2014) define new manufacturing technologies.

Beside the results, this present study assisted in filling the gap in the context of consumer behaviour for firm sustainability in the emerging nation such as Malaysia. This is because most prior studies focused on developed economy consumer market. Consequently, it is vital to link the existing research gaps between digital manufacturing and consumer behaviour which are necessary for firm sustainability in the current economic situation. There was no joint study on digital manufacturing on consumer behaviour, the mediating influence of the financial structure between technology, automation, industrial revolution and consumer behaviour in Malaysia. Hence, this study contributed to the existing body of literature through investigating the effect of digital manufacturing through its components (technology, automation and industrial revolution 4.0) on consumer behaviour for firm sustainability.

5. Limitations and Future Directions

The scope of this current study was restricted to Malaysia in terms of geographical areas. This study was a cross-sectional survey research. The study only considered the data obtained from manufacturing managers to assess their ability toward handling consumer behaviour to their business practices digital manufacturing was adopted. As such, future studies may consider including other service sectors and manufacturing firms as respondents to gain better ways of its operation. In addition, this study used one mediating variable, "financial structure", which provides a new direction for future research in digital manufacturing and consumer behaviour. Future researcher can advanced new studies in digital manufacturing which need to be explored in upcoming research. Finally, this study was conducted in a developing country, the research framework can be replicated in other emerging economy to observe its sustainability.

Conclusion

The main aim of this study was to investigate the effect of digital manufacturing on consumer behaviour for sustainability of firm and the mediating role of financial structure. This study has found that the first component of digital manufacturing, technology, automation and industrial revolution 4.0, have significant relationship on consumer behaviour; similarly, it technology, automation and IR 4.0 have significant and positive relationship with financial structure. Further, technology, automation and IR 4.0 were found to have indirect effect on consumer behaviour via the full mediation of financial structure. In summary, technology, automation and industrial revolution 4.0 has relation with consumer behaviour through full mediation of financial structure. This study has revealed that there was a positive links between digital manufacturing through its three components (technology, automation and IR 4.0) and consumer behaviour on firm sustainability in Malaysia. Digital manufacturing is a viable strategic planning mechanism which digital manufacturing managers need to scheme by recognising consumer behaviour on firm sustainability in Malaysia.

REFERENCE

Abisourour, Ahmed, (1994). The emerging arab capital markets: status. Role and development prospects," in SaidE1 Naggar, ed., financial policies and capital markets in Arab Countries. *Washington, D.C.: International Monetary Fund*

- (*Papers Presented at a Seminar held in Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates*), 54 - 87.
- Abu-Alkeir, N. I. & Area, S. (2020). Factors influencing consumers buying intentions towards electric cars: the Arab customers' perspective. *International Journal of Marketing Studies*, 12(2).
- Aghion, P., Bond, S., Klemm, A. & Marinescu, I. (2004). Technology and financial structure: are innovative firms different?. *Journal of the European Economic Association*, 2 (23), 277-288. doi.org/10.1162/154247604323067989.
- Ahmed, W., Najmi, A., Faizan, H. M. & Ahmed, S. (2019). Consumer behaviour towards willingness to pay for halal products. *British Food Journal*. 121(2), 492-504.
- Aivazian, V. A. & Berkowitz, M. K. (1998). Ex post production flexibility, asset specificity, and financial structure. *Journal of Accounting, Auditing & Finance*, 13(1), 1-20.
- Akter, S., Wamba, F. S. & Dewan, S. (2017). Why PLS-SEM is suitable for complex modeling? An empirical illustration in Big Data Analytics Quality. *Production Planning and Control*, 28 (11-12), 1011-1021.
- Albers, A., Gladysz, B., Pinner, T., Butenko, V. & Stürmlinger, T. (2016). Procedure for defining the system of objectives in the initial phase of an industry 4.0 project focusing on intelligent quality control systems. *Procedia Cirp*, 52(1), 262-267.
- Ambler, N. & Bui, T. (2011). Harnessing the influence of social proof in online shopping: The effect of electronic word of mouth on sales of digital microproducts. *International journal of electronic commerce*, 16(2), 91-114.
- Ameer, R. & Othman, R. (2012). Sustainability practices and corporate financial performance. A study based on the top global corporations. *Journal Business Ethics* 108(1), 61-79.
- Ansari, Z. A. (2019). Measuring online consumer behaviour: scale development & validation. *Journal of Business and Retail Management Research*, 13(3), 222-234.
- Armstrong, D. (2009). Bringing Hofstede home: Culture as an impetus for diverging consumer behaviour in the Local Market. In *Submission for the IACCM Conference* (24-26).
- Ashraf, S. (2019). Factors influencing consumers buying behaviour within the clothing industry. *Pakistan journal of art and culture (PJAC)*, 2(4), 1-12.
- Bardin, L. (2011). Análise de conteúdo (Edições 70). *Lisboa. Portugal*.
- Basile, V. (2019). Investigating new consumer behaviour dimensions in grocery retailing: some evidence from Southern Italy. *Journal of Business and Retail Management Research*, 14(01), 40-62.
- Bates, T. W., Du, F. & Wang, J. J. (2020). Workplace automation and corporate financial policy. doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3556935.
- Bates, T. W., Du, F. & Wang, J. J. (2020). Workplace automation and corporate financial policy. Available at SSRN 3556935.
- Beckett, A. G. (1998). *Strategy and consumer behaviour in the financial services industry: the role and significance of transaction relationships* (Doctoral dissertation, Loughborough University).
- Berkhout, F. & Hertin, J. (2004). De-materialising and re-materialising: digital technologies and the environment. *Futures*, 36(8), 903-920.
- Birkenmaier, J. & Fu, Q. J. (2019). Does consumer financial management behaviour relate to their financial access?. *Journal of Consumer Policy*, 42(3), 333-348.
- BMBF. Industries 4.0. Berlin: 2015.

- Bokrantz, J., Skoogh, A., Berlin, C. & Stahre, J. (2017). Maintenance in digitalised manufacturing: Delphi-based scenarios for 2030. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 191, 154-169.
- Brynjolfsson, E. & McAfee, A. (2014). *The second machine age: Work, progress, and prosperity in a time of brilliant technologies*, New York, W.W. Norton & Company
- Castelo-Branco, I., Cruz-Jesus, F. & Oliveira, T. (2019). Assessing Industry 4.0 readiness in manufacturing: Evidence for the European Union. *Computers in Industry*, 107, 22-32.
- Chakraborty, S., & Ray, T. (2007). The development and structure of financial systems. *Journal of Economic Dynamics and Control*, 31(9), 2920-2956.
- Chen, Y., Tang, G., Jin J., Li, J. & Paillé, P. (2015). Linking market orientation and environmental performance: the influence of environmental strategy, employee's environmental involvement, and environmental product quality. *Journal Business Ethics* 127(2):479-500.
- Cheng, C. M., G. W. Chan & M. A. Limayem. (2005). Critical review of online consumer behaviour: empirical research [J]. *Journal of Electronic Commerce in Organizations* 3(4), 1-19.
- Chittenden, F., Hall, G., & Hutchinson, P. (1996). Small firm growth, access to capital markets and financial structure: Review of issues and an empirical investigation. *Small business economics*, 8(1), 59-67.
- Chiu, T., Wang, Y. & Vasarhelyi, M. A. (2020). The automation of financial statement fraud detection: a framework using process mining. *Journal of Forensic and Investigative Accounting*, 12(1), 86-108.
- Chu, L. K. (2020). Financial structure and economic growth nexus revisited. *Borsa Istanbul Review*, 20(1), 24-36. doi.org/10.1016/j.bir.2019.08.003.
- Cirillo, V., Fanti, L., Mina, A. & Ricci, A. (2020). Digitizing firms: skills, work organization and the adoption of new enabling technologies. INAPP, Working Paper, WP. n 53, 1-27
- Comegys, C. & Brennan, M. L. (2003). Students' online shopping behaviour: A dual-country perspective. *Journal of Internet Commerce*, 2(2), 69-87. doi.org/10.1300/J179v02n02_05.
- Constantinides, E. (2004). Influencing the online consumer's behaviour: The Web experience. *Internet research*, 14(2), 111-126.
- Corò, G. & Volpe, M. (2020). 7 Driving factors in the adoption of industry 4.0 technologies. *Industry 4.0 and regional transformations*.
- Coze, Y., Kawaski, N., Kulka, T., Sire, P., Sottcasa, P. & Bloem, J. (2009). *Virtual concept. Real profit with digital manufacturing and simulation*, Dassault Systèmes & Sogeti, Paris. Netherland.
- Cruz-Cárdenas, J., Zabelina, E., Deyneka, O., Guadalupe-Lanas, J., & Velín-Fárez, M. (2019). Role of demographic factors, attitudes toward technology, and cultural values in the prediction of technology-based consumer behaviours: A study in developing and emerging countries. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 149, 119768.
- da Silva, E. H. D. R., Shinohara, A. C., de Lima, E. P., Angelis, J. & Machado, C. G. (2019). Reviewing digital manufacturing concept in the industry 4.0 paradigm. *Procedia CIRP*, 81, 240-245. doi.org/10.1016/j.procir.2019.03.042.

- Da Silva, V. L., Kovaleski, J. L. & Pagani, R. N. (2018). Technology transfer in the supply chain oriented to industry 4.0: A literature review. *Technology Annals of Strategic Management*, 31, 546-562
- Dahlin, P., Ekman, P., Røndell, J. & Pesämaa, O. (2020). Exploring the business logic behind CSR certifications. *Journal of Business Research*, 112, 521-530.
- Darley, W. K., Blankson, C. & Luethge, D. J. (2010). Toward an integrated framework for online consumer behaviour and decision-making process: A review. *Psychology & marketing*, 27(2), 94-116.
- Davis, E. P. (1996). The role of institutional investors in the evolution of financial structure and behaviour. *The Future of the Financial System*, 33, 49-99.
- Demangeot, C. & Broderick, A. J. (2007). Conceptualising consumer behaviour in online shopping environments.
- Dennis, C., Merrilees, B. Jayawardhena, C. & Tiu Wright, L. (2009). E-consumer behaviour. *European journal of Marketing*, 43(9/10), 1121-1139.
- do Paco, A., Shiel, C., & Alves, H. (2019). A new model for testing green consumer behaviour. *Journal of cleaner production*, 207, 998-1006. doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2015.11.005.
- Echekoba, F. & Ananwude, A. (2016). The effect of financial structure on the performance of Nigeria consumer goods firms. *Journal of Scientific Research & Reports*, 10(4), 1-15.
- Echekoba, F., & Ananwude, A. (2016). The effect of financial structure on the performance of Nigeria consumer goods firms. *Journal of Scientific Research & Reports*, 10(4), 1-15.
- Ehret, M. & Wirtz, J. (2017). Unlocking value from machines: business models and the industrial internet of things. *Journal of Marketing Management*, 33(1-2), 111-130.
- Erikson, Kai (1986). On Work and Alienation,” *American Sociological Review*, 51 (1), 1-8.
- Erkol, Y. A., Coşkun, N. (2020). The impact of financial structure on export performance: the case of manufacturing sectors in Turkey. *Alanya Academic Review Journal*, 4(3), 963- 974.
- Fain, D., & Roberts, M. L. (1997). Technology vs. consumer behaviour: the battle for the financial services customer. *Journal of Direct Marketing*, 11(1), 44-54.
- Ferri, M. G. & Jones, W. H. (1979). Determinants of financial structure: A new methodological approach. *The Journal of finance*, 34(3), 631-644. doi. 10.2307/2327431.
- Folkes, V. S. (1988). Recent attribution research in consumer behaviour: A review and new directions. *Journal of consumer research*, 14(4), 548-565.
- Frank, A. G., Mendes, G. H., Ayala, N. F. & Ghezzi, A. (2019). Servitization and Industry 4.0 convergence in the digital transformation of product firms: A business model innovation perspective. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, in press.
- Frohm, J., Lindström, V., Stahre, J. & Winroth, M. (2008). Levels of automation in manufacturing. *Ergonomia-an International journal of ergonomics and human factors*, 30(3), 1-36.
- García-Muiña, F. E., Medina-Salgado, M. S., Ferrari, A. M. & Cucchi, M. (2020). Sustainability transition in industry 4.0 and smart manufacturing with the triple-layered business model canvas. *Sustainability*, 12(6), 2364. doi.org/10.3390/su12062364.
- Gasanov, E. A., Zubarev, A. E. & Krasota, T. G. (2020, March). Digital technologies as a factor for growth of continuous well-being of sovereign consumers in the modern

- society. *In International Scientific Conference" Far East Con"(ISCFEC 2020) (pp. 1229-1243). Atlantis Press. doi.org/10.2991/aebmr.k.200312.170.*
- Gertler, M. L. (1988). *Financial structure and aggregate economic activity: an overview* (No. w2559). National Bureau of Economic Research.
- Ghobakhloo, M. (2020). Industry 4.0, digitization, and opportunities for sustainability. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 252, 119869. doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.119869.
- Gillani, F., Chatha, K. A., Jajja, M. S. S. & Farooq, S. (2020). Implementation of digital manufacturing technologies: Antecedents and consequences. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 107748. doi:10.1016/j.ijpe.2020.107748.
- Graessley, S.; Horak, J., Kovacova, M., Valaskova, K. & Poliak, M.J. (2019). Consumer attitudes and behaviours in the technology-driven sharing economy: Motivations for participating in collaborative consumption. *Journal of Self-Government Management Economics*, 7, 25-30.
- Groover, M. P. (2001). *Automation, production systems, and computer-integrated manufacturing. Prentice Hall, Upper Saddle River, N. J, USA.*
- Hair, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C. M. & Sarstedt, M. A (2017). *Primer on partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM)*, 2nd ed.; SAGE: Los Angeles, CA, USA.
- Hair, J. F., Risher, J. J., Sarstedt, M. & Ringle, C. M. (2019). When to use and how to report the results of PLS-SEM. *European Business Review*, 31(1), 2-24.
- Hair, J., Hult, T., Ringle, C. & Sarstedt, M. (2017). *A primer on partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM)*, 2nd ed., Sage Publications.
- Hamilton, R. W., Mittal, C., Shah, A., Thompson, D. V. & Griskevicius, V. (2019). How financial constraints influence consumer behaviour: An integrative framework. *Journal of Consumer Psychology*, 29(2), 285-305.
- Hansen, T. (2008). Consumer values, the theory of planned behaviour and online grocery shopping. *International Journal of Consumer Studies*, 32(2), 128-137.
- Hartmann, B., King, W. P. & Narayanan, S. (2015). *Digital manufacturing: The revolution will be virtualized. McKinsey & Company.*
- Hayhoe, T., Podhorska, I., Siekelova, A. & Stehel, V. (2019). Sustainable manufacturing in Industry 4.0: Cross-sector networks of multiple supply chains, cyber-physical production systems, and AI-driven decision-making. *Journal of Self-Governance and Management Economics*, 7(2), 31-36.
- Hermann, M., Pentek, T. & Otto, B. (2016). Design principles for industry 4.0 scenarios, in: *2016 49th Hawaii International Conference on System Sciences (HICSS), IEEE*, 3928- 3937.
- Heyman, D., Deloof, M. & Ooghe, H. (2008). The financial structure of private held Belgian firms. *Small business economics*, 30(3), 301-313.
- Hoffmann, P., Laeven, L. & Ratnovski, L. (2020). Financial intermediation and technology: what's old, what's new?. ECB Working Paper Series No 2438 / July 2020, 1-33. doi.10.2866/73816.
- Hogg, M., Askegaard, S., Bamossy, G. & Solomon, M. (2006). *Consumer behaviour: a European perspective*. 3rd ed. Harlow: Prentice Hall, 51-76.
- Holmström, J., Liotta, G., & Chaudhuri, A. (2017). Sustainability outcomes through direct digital manufacturing-based operational practices: A design theory approach. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 167, 951-961. doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2017.03.092.

- Horák, J. (2016). Does industry 4.0 influence efficiency of financial management of a company? *The 10th International Days of Statistics and Economics, Prague, September 8-10*, 574-582.
- Hsieh, J., Chen, T. C. & Lin, S. C. (2019). Financial structure, bank competition and income inequality. *The North American Journal of Economics and Finance*, 48, 450-466. doi.org/10.1016/j.najef.2019.03.006.
- Huyghebaert, N. & Van de Gucht, L. M. (2007). The determinants of financial structure: new insights from business start-ups. *European Financial Management*, 13(1), 101-133.
- Imran, M., Hameed, U. W. & Haque, U. D. (2018). Influence of industry 4.0 on the production and service sectors in Pakistan: Evidence from textile and logistics industries. *Social Sciences*, 7(12), 246.
- Imran, M., Hameed, W. Haque, A. (2018). Influence of industry 4.0 on the production and service sectors in Pakistan: Evidence from textile and logistics industries. *Social Sciences*, 7(12), 246. doi.org/10.3390/socsci7120246.
- Indahingwati, A., Launtu, A., Tamsah, H., Firman, A., Putra, A. H. P. K., & Aswari, A. (2019). How digital technology driven millennial consumer behaviour in Indonesia. *The Journal of Distribution Science*, 17(8), 25-34.
- Johnson, D. J. (1981). The behavior of financial structure and sustainable growth in an inflationary environment. *Financial Management*, 10(4), 30. doi:10.2307/3665216
- Jose, J. (2017). Impact of technology on consumer behaviour. *IRA-International Journal of Management & Social Sciences*, 6(2), 264-267.
- Kerin, R. A., Jain, A. & Howard, D. J. (1992). Store shopping experience and consumer price- quality-value perceptions. *Journal of Retailing*, 68(4), 376-387.
- Khan, M. M., Asad, H. & Mehboob, I. (2017). Investigating the consumer behaviour for halal endorsed products: Case of an emerging Muslim market. *Journal of Islamic Marketing*, 8(4), 625-641.
- Khare, A. & Rakesh, S. (2011). Antecedents of online shopping behavior in India: An examination. *Journal of Internet Commerce*, 10, 227-244.
- Kiran, R., Sharma, A., & Mittal, K. C. (2008). Attitudes, preferences and profile of online buyers in India: Changing trends. *South Asian Journal of Management*, 15(3), 56-73.
- Kock, N. (2015). Common method bias in PLS-SEM: A full collinearity assessment approach. *International Journal of e-Collaboration*, 11(4), 1-10.
- Kock, N. (2017). Common method bias: A full collinearity assessment method for PLS-SEM. In *Partial least squares path modeling* (pp. 245-257). Springer.
- Kramer, R. M. & Porter, M. (2011). Creating shared value. *Harvard Business Review*, 89 (1/2), 62-77
- Lawless, M., O'Connell, B. & O'Toole, C. (2015). Financial structure and diversification of European firms. *Applied Economics*, 47(23), 2379-2398.
- Lee, K. S., Ahn, K. M & Shin, Y. J. (2004). A study on the post-1997 financial structure as influenced by the managerial characteristics of Korean shipping firms. *Journal of Shipping and Logistics*, 42, 21-43
- Lee, S. Y., Kim, Y. D. & Ahn, K. M. (2019). A study on the financial structure effect factor and business analysis of ocean shipping companies. *Journal of Navigation and Port Research*, 43(4), 264-272.
- Lin, J. Y., Sun, X. & Jiang, Y. (2009). Toward a theory of optimal financial structure. *The World Bank*. 1-29, doi.org/10.1596/1813-9450-5038.

- Lindström, V. (2008). Formulation of automation strategy in manufacturing systems: developing a methodology for analysing and choosing levels of automation (Doctoral dissertation, Chalmers University of Technology). *Jönköping University*.
- Linner, T. (2013). *Automated and robotic construction: integrated automated construction sites* (Doctoral dissertation, Technische Universität München).
- MacKay, P. (2003). Real flexibility and financial structure: An empirical analysis. *Review of Financial Studies*, 16(4), 1131-1165.
- Martiskova, P. & Svec, R. (2019). Digital era and consumer behaviour on the internet. in international scientific conference “digital transformation of the economy: challenges, trends, new opportunities” (pp. 92-100). Springer, Cham.
- Martiskova, P. & Svec, R. (2019). Digital Era and Consumer Behaviour on the Internet. In *International Scientific Conference “Digital Transformation of the Economy: Challenges, Trends, New Opportunities”* (pp. 92-100). Springer, Cham.
- Metallo, C., Agrifoglio, R., Schiavone, F. & Mueller, J. (2018). Understanding business model in the internet of things industry. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 136, 298-306.
- Migdał-Najman, K., Najman, K., & Badowska, S. (2020). The GNG neural network in analyzing consumer behaviour patterns: empirical research on a purchasing behaviour processes realized by the elderly consumers. *Advances in Data Analysis and Classification*, 1-36.
- Moeuf, A., Pellerin, R., Lamouri, S., Tamayo-Giraldo, S. & Barbaray, R. (2018). The industrial management of SMEs in the era of Industry 4.0. *International Journal of Production Research*, 56(3), 1118-1136. doi.org/10.1080/00207543.2017.1372647.
- Müller, J. M., Buliga, O. & Voigt, K. I. (2018). Fortune favors the prepared: How SMEs approach business model innovations in Industry 4.0. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 132, 2-17.
- Murray, K. B. & Vogel, C. M. (1997). Using a hierarchy-of-effects approach to gauge the effectiveness of corporate social responsibility to generate good will toward the firm: financial versus non-financial impacts. *Journal of Business Research*, 38, 141-59.
- Namazi, M. & Namazi, N. (2016). Conceptual analysis of moderator and mediator variables in business research. *Procedia Economics and Finance* 36, 540 - 554.
- Niaki, M. K., Torabi, S. A. & Nonino, F. (2019). Why manufacturers adopt additive manufacturing technologies: The role of sustainability. *Journal of cleaner production*, 222, 381-392. doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.03.019.
- Nicholls, A. & Lee, N. (2006). Purchase decision-making in fair trade and the ethical purchase ‘gap’: “Is there a fair trade twix?”. *Journal of Strategic Marketing*, 14(4), 369-386.
- Nimfa, T. D., Latiff, A. S. A. & Wahab, S. A. (2020). Instrument for testing innovation on the sustainable growth of manufacturing SMEs in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Management Sciences*, 3(2), 57-70. [doi.10.30560/jems.v3n2p57](https://doi.org/10.30560/jems.v3n2p57).
- Nimfa, T. D. & Goyit, G. M. (2016). Technology business incubation and entrepreneurial opportunity for economic development in plateau state. *2nd International Entrepreneurship Research Conference: 'Innovative Entrepreneurship for Sustainable Economic Development' at Entrepreneurship Development Centre, Nasarawa State University, Keffi. Nasarawa State, Nigeria*, 2.

- Nimfa, T. D., Yunus, M. B. R. M., Latiff, A. S. A., Mahmood, R. & Wahab, A. S. (2019). Sustainable innovation and creativity for value creation: A study of hospitality enterprises in Jos Metropolis, Nigeria. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 11(26) 35-48. doi: 10.7176/ejbm
- Nor-Aishah, H., Ahmad, N. H. & Thurasamy, R. (2020). Entrepreneurial leadership and sustainable performance of manufacturing SMEs in Malaysia: the contingent role of entrepreneurial bricolage. *Sustainability*, 12(8), 3100.
- Nyame-Asiamah, F. & Kawalek, P. (2020). Sustainability and consumer behaviour: towards a coherent emergent theory. *The Palgrave Handbook of Corporate Social Responsibility*, 1-18.
- Ong, V., Yee, N. M., Hui, G. J., Kasim, N. & Hizza, I. (2015). The impact of service automation on customer satisfaction and customer retention: An empirical study of Malaysian rail transportation. In *Proceeding of 4th global business and finance research conference*, World Business Institute, Melbourne.
- Ordieres-Meré, J., Remón, T. P. & Rubio, J. (2020). Digitalization: An opportunity for contributing to sustainability from knowledge creation. *Sustainability*, 12(4), 1460.
- Oro, O. U. & Ekpo, A. H. (2020). The value of the financial structure to economic performance in oil-producing countries. *OPEC Energy Review*, 44(1), 43-58.
- Paddeu, D. & Parkhurst, G. (2020). The potential for automation to transform urban deliveries: Drivers, barriers and policy priorities. Elsevier.
- Pantano, E. (2011). Cultural factors affecting consumer behaviour: a new perception model. *EuroMed Journal of Business*, 6(1), 117-136.
- Parasuraman, R. & Riley, V. (1997). Humans and automation: use, misuse, disuse, abuse. *Human Factors*, 39 (2), 230-53. doi.org/10.1518/001872097778543886.
- Parasuraman, R., Sheridan, T. B. & Wickens, C. D. (2000). A model for types and levels of human interaction with automation. *IEEE transactions on systems, man, and Cybernetics*, 30, 286-297. doi. 10.1109/3468.844354.
- Perez, A. & del Bosque, I. R. (2009). The social role of financial companies as a determinant of consumer behaviour. *International Journal of Bank Marketing*. 27(6), 467-485
- Pickard, M., Grecu, I. & Grecu, G. (2019). Sustainable smart manufacturing in Industry 4.0: Real-time resource planning, process monitoring, and production control. *Economics, Management and Financial Markets*, 14(3), 30-36.
- Rajbhandary, A. (1999). Financial structure and real behaviour of firms in developing economies. *Emory University, ProQuest Dissertations Publishing*, 1-50.
- Ramayah, T., Cheah, J.; Chuah, F., Ting, H. & Memon, M.A. (2018). Partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM) Using SmartPLS 3.0, 2nd ed.; Pearson: Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia.
- Razak, D. A., Abdullah, M. A. & Ersoy, A. (2018). Small medium enterprises (SMES) in Turkey and Malaysia a comparative discussion on issues and challenges. *International Journal of Business, Economics and Law*, 10(49), 2-591.
- Reed II, A., Forehand, M. R., Puntoni, S. & Warlop, L. (2012). Identity-based consumer behavior. *International Journal of Research in Marketing*, 29(4), 310-321. doi.org/10.1016/j.ijresmar.2012.08.002.
- Reisch, L. A. & Zhao, M. (2017). Behavioural economics, consumer behaviour and consumer policy: state of the art. *Behavioural Public Policy*, 1(2), 190-206.

- Richarme, M., (2007). Consumer decision-making models, strategies, and theories. [www.decisionanalyst.com/Downloads/Consumer Decision Making.pdf](http://www.decisionanalyst.com/Downloads/Consumer_Decision_Making.pdf). (Accessed September 26, 2020).
- Rifkin, Jeremy (1996). The end of work. New York: Putnam.
- Rogers, E.M. (1983). Diffusion of innovations, (Third Edition), New York: The Free Press.
- Rogers, E.M. (1995). Diffusion of innovations, (Fourth Edition), New York: The Free Press.
- Royle, J. & Laing, A. (2014). The digital marketing skills gap: developing a digital marketer model for the communication industries. *International Journal of Information Management*, 34(2), 65-73.
- Salomon, F. & Klaus-Jürgen, G. S. (2017). Financial innovation and monetary policy: challenges and prospects. Policy department a: economic and scientific policy. [http://www.europarl.europa.eu/regdata/etudes/idan/2017/602045/ipo_id_a\(2017\)602045_en.pdf](http://www.europarl.europa.eu/regdata/etudes/idan/2017/602045/ipo_id_a(2017)602045_en.pdf).
- Saraswati, B. D., Maski, G., Kaluge, D. & Sakti, R. K. (2020). The effect of financial inclusion and financial technology on effectiveness of the Indonesian monetary policy. *Business: Theory and Practice*, 21(1), 230-243. doi.org/10.3846/btp.2020.10396.
- Sarstedt, M., Hair Jr, J. F., Nitzl, C., Ringle, C. M. & Howard, M. C. (2020). Beyond a tandem analysis of SEM and PROCESS: Use of PLS-SEM for mediation analyses!. *International Journal of Market Research*, 62(3), 288-299.
- Schiffman, L. G. & Kanuk, L. L. (2007). Consumer behaviour, 9th ed, New Jersey: Prentice Hall, 55-63.
- Sima, V., Gheorghie, I. G., Subić, J. & Nancu, D. (2020). Influences of the industry 4.0 revolution on the human capital development and consumer behaviour: a systematic review. *Sustainability*, 12(10), 4035.
- SME Corp. Malaysia. (2015). [Online] Available: <http://www.smecorp.gov.my/vn2/SME>.
- Srai, J. S. (2019). Shaping the future of global manufacturing supply networks: programme & abstracts. <https://doi.org/10.17863/CAM.45918>.
- Srinivasan, S., Rutz, O. J. & Pauwels, K. (2016). Paths to and off purchase: quantifying the impact of traditional marketing and online consumer activity. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 44(4), 440-453. doi.org/10.1007/s11747-015-0431-z.
- Sudbury-Riley, L. & Kohlbacher, F. (2016). Ethically minded consumer behaviour: Scale review, development, and validation. *Journal of Business Research*, 69(8), 2697-2710.
- Sue, Y. (2015). The impact of digital technology on consumer purchase behaviour. *Journal of Financial Perspectives*, 3(3), 1-10. <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3084041>.
- Tamari, M. (1980). The financial structure of the small firm - an international comparison of corporate accounts in the USA, France, UK, Israel, and Japan. *American Journal of Small Business*, 4(4), 20-34.
- Tuffnell, C., Kral, P., Durana, P. & Krulicky, T. (2019). Industry 4.0-based manufacturing systems: Smart production, sustainable supply chain networks, and real-time process monitoring. *Journal of Self-Governance and Management Economics*, 7(2), 7-12.
- Ugurlu, M. (1997). International corporate alliances and financial structure: a comparative study on the Turkish manufacturing industry. *Cross Cultural Management: An International Journal*. 4(4), 29-40. doi.org/10.1108/eb008428.
- UshaVaidehi, P. (2014). Factors influencing online shopping behavior of students in engineering colleges at Rangareddy district. *Sumedha Journal of*

- Management*, 3(1), 50-62. Vidyavihar, S. (2015). *Foundation*. Retrieved from http://www.somaiya.edu/VidyaVihar/somaiya/get_to_know_us/foundation.
- Vanhanen, J. (2020). Automation of financial management processes by utilizing robotic process automation: a Finnish banking case. <http://urn.fi/urn:nbn:fi-fe202001081475>.
- Wang, R. & Li, R. (2020, February). Innovation of university financial management model based on big data technology. In the international conference on cyber security intelligence and analytics (pp. 337-344). Springer, Cham. doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-43309-3_47
- Worldwide, S. (2018). Retail e-Commerce sales worldwide from 2014 to 2021 (in billion USDollars). <https://www.statista.com/statistics/379046/worldwide-retail-E-commerce-sales/> (accessed on 2 August 2018).
- Wright, A. (2020). How technology and a changing consumer behaviour instigated change in the Deutsche Post DHL Group: An analysis on organizational change. *Bachelor of Commerce Best Business Research Papers*. Gustavson School of Business, University of Victoria, 1-116.
- Wu, J. F. & Chang, Y. P. (2016). Multichannel integration quality, online perceived value and online purchase intention. *Internet Research*. A perspective of land-based retailers. *Internet Research*, 26(5), 1228-1248. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IntR-04-2014-0111>
- Yasav, S. (2015). The impact of digital technology on consumer purchase behaviour. *Journal of Financial Perspectives*, 3(3), 1-13.
- Zaki, M., Theodoulidis, B., Shapira, P., Neely, A. & Surekli, E. (2017). The role of big data to facilitate redistributed manufacturing using a co-creation lens: patterns from consumer goods. *Procedia CIRP*, 63, 680-685.
- Zhou, Z., Xie, S. S. & Chen, D. (2011). Fundamentals of digital manufacturing science. *Springer Science & Business Media*.